

Knowledge, dietary habits, and perception of hypertension risk factors among undergraduates in Owerri

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Abstract

Hypertension is a major global health challenge and a leading cause of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. This study examined dietary practices, knowledge, and perceptions of hypertension among 438 undergraduate students at the Federal University of Technology, Owerri, using a structured questionnaire. Knowledge about hypertension was high (89%), but misconceptions persisted, with 69.6% believing hypertension presents with early symptoms. Informal sources were the predominant means of knowledge acquisition (62.6%), raising concerns about accuracy. Dietary patterns revealed frequent consumption of starchy foods, sugary beverages, and energy drinks, which are linked to increased hypertension risk, alongside moderate intake of fruits and vegetables. Positive perceptions regarding salt reduction (92.4%) and exercise (80.8%) suggest effective public health messaging, yet gaps remain concerning processed foods and beverage-related risks. No significant association was found between starch and beverage consumption and knowledge levels across genders. However, a significant association was observed between dietary practices and perceptions among females ($p = 0.005$), suggesting gender differences in how diet influences attitudes towards hypertension. These findings emphasize that awareness alone does not consistently translate into healthier practices. Targeted, gender-sensitive interventions that integrate accurate health education with behavioral strategies, environmental supports, and access to affordable healthy foods are needed. Strengthening campus-based health promotion programs to correct misconceptions and encourage healthier eating behaviors is critical for reducing hypertension risk and improving long-term health outcomes among university students.

Keywords: Hypertension; Risk Factors; Perception; Dietary Habits

1. Introduction

Hypertension, commonly referred to as high blood pressure, is a condition characterized by persistently elevated pressure within the blood vessels. Blood is circulated from the heart to the rest of the body through these vessels, and with each heartbeat, the heart generates pressure by pumping blood into the arteries. Blood pressure results from the force exerted by circulating blood against arterial walls, and excessive pressure increases the workload of the heart. Hypertension is a major medical concern as it significantly raises the risk of cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, renal, and other systemic diseases. Globally, it is one of the leading causes of premature mortality, affecting more than one billion people, approximately one in four men and one in five women. Low- and middle-income countries bear the greatest burden, accounting for nearly two-thirds of cases, a trend linked to the rising prevalence of modifiable risk factors in these populations (1).

The current definition of hypertension (HTN) is systolic blood pressure (SBP) values of 130 mm Hg or more and/or diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of more than 80 mm Hg (2). As one of the most important contributors to cardiovascular

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and renal diseases worldwide, hypertension accounts for more than 10 million deaths annually. In Nigeria, its prevalence has been rising steadily over recent decades, with regional estimates ranging from 22% to 44% (3). The university setting in Nigeria represents a critical developmental stage, where young adults transition to independent living and begin making autonomous lifestyle choices, including dietary habits (4). These changes often foster unhealthy behaviors that increase susceptibility to hypertension. Beyond lifestyle factors, the level of knowledge and perception of hypertension within this demographic also strongly influences risk.

As a chronic non-communicable disease, hypertension presents a substantial public health challenge both globally and in Nigeria. Recent evidence highlights the growing prevalence among young adults, including undergraduate students in Nigerian universities. The increasing adoption of unhealthy dietary practices, compounded by limited awareness of hypertension and its associated risks, may be driving this trend. While dietary behavior is a critical determinant in the development and management of hypertension (5), there remains a limited understanding of how undergraduate students in Nigerian universities perceive the condition and how their knowledge and dietary practices shape their risk. This study aimed to explore the dietary habits, knowledge, and perception of risk factors of hypertension among undergraduate students at the Federal University of Technology, Owerri.

1.1. Research Hypothesis

H₀ (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant association between knowledge of hypertension risk factors and dietary habits of undergraduate students in Owerri.

H_A (Alternate Hypothesis): There is a significant association between knowledge of hypertension risk factors and dietary habits of undergraduate students in Owerri.

2. Materials and Methods

This study was a cross-sectional descriptive study. The Federal University of Technology Owerri (FUTO) is a Federal Government-owned University in Owerri West, Owerri, the capital of Imo State, Nigeria. The National Universities Commission's recommendation that a minimum area of ten thousand (10,000) acres, or 4,048 hectares, should be obtained based on the location, the relative lack of human settlements within the area, and other pertinent factors served as the basis for the site's selection. It is situated 25 kilometers south of Owerri.

The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula,

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)}$$

Sample size calculated with 10% non-response rate was 438.

Multi-stage simple random sampling procedure was used for this study.

2.1. Stage 1: Selection of Faculties

Simple random sampling was used to select 5 faculties out of the 11 in the University. This was done via balloting without replacement to give every faculty in the university an equal chance of being selected.

2.2. Stage 2: Selection of departments

Simple random sampling was used to select 2 departments from each of the 5 faculties that were randomly selected in the study area. This was done via balloting without replacement to give every department an equal chance of being selected.

2.3. Stage 3: Selection of level/ year of study

Simple random sampling was used to select 3 levels from each of the 2 departments previously selected. This was done via balloting without replacement to give every level an equal chance of being selected.

2.4. Stage 4: Selection of respondents

In each of the selected levels, respondents who gave consent were included in the study until the desired number was reached.

The instrument for data collection was a structured, validated self-administered questionnaire. A total of four hundred and thirty-eight (438) copies of questionnaires were distributed to the students and the same number were retrieved. The questionnaire was divided into four sections: (Section A: Socio-demographic characteristics; Section B: Knowledge about hypertension risk factors; Section C: Perception toward hypertension; and Section D: Dietary habits of respondents).

The purpose of the research was explained to each respondent, and verbal informed consent was obtained from them before inclusion in the study. Also, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured. The confidentiality of the information they gave was maintained. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 was used in the analysis of the data obtained from the study.

3. Results

Table 1 below shows the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents. Among the respondents, 282 are female, constituting the majority at 64.4%, while 156 are male, making up 35.6% of the sample. The majority of respondents, 263, fall within the 21-26 age group, comprising 60.0% of the sample. 137 respondents are aged 15-20, representing 31.3%, while only 38 respondents, or 8.7%, are 27 years and above. The highest representation is from 500-level students, with 158 respondents, accounting for 36.1% of the sample. 116 respondents from 300 level constitute 26.5%.

A vast majority of respondents, 422, are single, making up 96.3% of the sample. Only 13 respondents are married, representing 3.0%. The largest group of respondents, 52.5% hail from Imo State. Several respondents, 206, have a monthly allowance of less than 20,000 Naira, comprising 47.0% of the sample. 45 respondents have an allowance above 50,000 Naira, making up 10.3%. The majority of respondents, 309, occupy positions within the first to third birth order in their families, accounting for 70.5% of the sample. 129 respondents, or 29.5%, are from the fourth birth order and above.

Table 1 Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender			
Female	282	64.4	64.4
Male	156	35.6	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0
Age			
15-20	137	31.3	31.3
21-26	263	60.0	91.3
27 and above	38	8.7	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0
Current level			
100 L	61	13.9	13.9
200 L	51	11.6	25.6
300 L	116	26.5	52.1
400 L	49	11.2	63.2
500 L	158	36.1	99.3
600 L	3	0.7	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0
Marital status			

Married	13	3.0	3.0
Single	422	96.3	99.3
Widowed	3	0.7	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0
Monthly allowance			
20,000 - 30,000	117	26.7	26.7
30,001 - 40,000	52	11.9	38.6
40,001 - 50,000	18	4.1	42.7
Above 50,000	45	10.3	53.0
Less than 20,000	206	47.0	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0
Position in the family			
1st - 3 rd	309	70.5	70.5
4th & above	129	29.5	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Table 2 below summarizes findings on the knowledge of hypertension risk factors and causes. The findings indicate that a substantial majority of respondents (89%) have heard of hypertension, whereas only 11% reported no prior knowledge. This high awareness level suggests that public health education and general exposure to information about hypertension have been somewhat effective. However, the presence of individuals who remain unaware highlights the need for continued awareness campaigns, particularly targeting vulnerable or less-informed populations.

Analysis of the sources of information about hypertension revealed that the most common source was categorized as “Others” (62.6%), likely encompassing interpersonal communication through family, friends, and community networks. Formal education accounted for 20% of awareness, while social media (9.2%) and internet resources (8.2%) were less frequently cited. These findings imply that informal social channels play a predominant role in knowledge dissemination. While this may enhance reach, it also increases the potential for misinformation. Consequently, there is an urgent need to integrate accurate health information into both formal education and digital media platforms to strengthen the reliability of information available to the public.

Respondents’ knowledge regarding specific characteristics of hypertension varied considerably:

The majority (86.1%) recognized that hypertension is linked to several risk factors, although a small proportion (3%) disagreed, and 10.9% were uncertain, suggesting incomplete understanding among some individuals. While 74.2% correctly identified hypertension as a chronic disease, 14.8% disagreed, reflecting a misconception that could impact treatment adherence.

A significant proportion (80.4%) understood the relationship between hypertension and cardiovascular complications. However, 8.7% did not recognize this association, indicating a need for enhanced cardiovascular risk education.

Nearly universal awareness (88.4%) was observed regarding the fact that hypertension affects both men and women, signifying a strong general understanding in this domain. Awareness that hypertension can be hereditary was reported by 74.2% of respondents, whereas 14.2% disagreed and 11.6% were uncertain, highlighting confusion about genetic predisposition.

Approximately 71.5% identified a sedentary lifestyle as a contributing factor, yet 15.5% disagreed, underscoring a lack of recognition of behavioral risk factors. Over half (56.6%) believed that hypertension can be cured, while 31.7% disagreed. This reflects a critical misconception, as hypertension is generally a lifelong condition that can be managed rather than cured.

A majority (69.6%) believed that hypertension presents symptoms at an early stage, which is inaccurate for many cases. This misunderstanding could lead to delayed diagnosis and treatment, given that hypertension is often asymptomatic in its initial stages. A high proportion (85.2%) correctly acknowledged that hypertension can lead to sudden death, demonstrating awareness of its severity.

Overall, the data demonstrate a relatively high level of awareness regarding hypertension, with strong knowledge of its seriousness and association with heart disease. However, several misconceptions persist, particularly concerning its curability, asymptomatic nature, and genetic basis. These gaps in understanding have significant implications for preventive strategies and treatment adherence.

Table 2 Knowledge about Hypertension Risk Factors

Variable	Response	Frequency	Percent
Hypertension	Heard of Hypertension		
	No	48	11.0
	Yes	390	89.0
	Total	438	100.0
	Source of Information		
	School	78	20.0
	Social media	36	9.2
	Internet	32	8.2
	Others	244	62.6
	No response	48	10.9
	Total	438	100.0
Hypertension Factors	Hypertension is Linked to Many Factors		
	No	13	3.0
	Yes	377	86.1
	Uncertain	48	10.9
	Total	438	100.0
	Hypertension is a Chronic Disease		
	No	65	14.8
	Yes	325	74.2
	Uncertain	48	10.9
	Total	438	100.0
	Hypertension is Associated with Heart Disease		
	No	38	8.7
	Yes	352	80.4
Uncertain	48	10.9	
Total	438	100.0	
Hypertension Can Affect Both Genders			
No	3	0.7	
Yes	387	88.4	

	Uncertain	48	10.9
	Total	438	100.0
	Hypertension Can Be Genetic		
	No	62	14.2
	Yes	325	74.2
	Uncertain	51	11.6
	Total	438	100.0
	Hypertension is Linked to Sedentary Lifestyle		
	No	68	15.5
	Yes	313	71.5
	Uncertain	57	13.0
	Total	438	100.0
	Hypertension Can Be Cured		
	No	139	31.7
	Yes	248	56.6
	Uncertain	51	11.6
	Total	438	100.0
	Hypertension Has Symptoms at the Early Stage		
	No	82	18.7
	Yes	305	69.6
	Uncertain	51	11.6
	Total	438	100.0
	Hypertension Can Lead to Sudden Death		
	No	17	3.9
	Yes	373	85.2
	Uncertain	48	10.9
	Total	438	100.0

Table 3 below summarizes the respondents' perception of hypertension.

47% positive perception means that less than half of respondents disagree that "Hypertension is not a disease." This suggests a significant misconception: many people may not view hypertension as a serious medical condition, which could affect early detection and treatment.

Only 18.9% positive perception for "Hypertension is found in only older people" indicates that most respondents think hypertension is mainly an old-age problem, which is a misconception. This perception can result in an underestimation of risk in younger adults, delaying prevention strategies.

92.4% positive perception on reducing salt intake is very high, showing strong awareness of dietary risk factors. This is encouraging and suggests that public health messages on salt reduction are effective.

60% positive perception for “Hypertension is more common among rich people” means that many people still associate it with affluence. While historically considered a “disease of affluence,” this is outdated because hypertension now affects all social classes. Misconception here could lead to risk neglect in lower-income groups.

53.1% positive perception about processed food causing hypertension shows moderate awareness. Nearly half are unsure or disagree, which means that more education is needed about processed foods and salt content.

80.8% positive perception that exercise reduces BP is very high. This reflects a good understanding of lifestyle interventions, although about 20% still doubt this, which is concerning.

A 72.4% positive perception indicates that most people correctly associate fried foods with an increased risk of hypertension. This is positive, but 21.5% neutrality or disagreement suggests some gaps in awareness.

A 68.9% positive perception indicates that a majority believe fruits and vegetables are beneficial, but a significant 31% either agree they are not or are neutral, which is a major misconception.

A 53.2% positive perception indicates a mixed understanding of the relationship between seasoning cubes and blood pressure. This is a critical gap, as seasoning cubes are common in many diets and are high in sodium, which can increase blood pressure.

Table 3 Perception of Hypertension

Hypertension is not a disease

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	73	16.7
Agree	99	22.6
Neutral	60	13.7
Disagree	124	28.3
Strongly Disagree	82	18.7
Total	438	100
Positive perception: 47%		

Hypertension is found only in older people

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	118	26.9
Agree	160	36.5
Neutral	77	17.6
Disagree	64	14.6
Strongly Disagree	19	4.3
Total	438	100
Positive perception: 18.9%		

Reducing salt intake is good

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	3	0.7
Disagree	6	1.4
Neutral	24	5.5
Agree	157	35.8
Strongly Agree	248	56.6
Total	438	100
Positive perception: 92.4%		

Hypertension is more common among rich people

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	15	3.4
Agree	24	5.5
Neutral	136	31.1
Disagree	163	37.2
Strongly Disagree	100	22.8
Total	438	100
Positive perception: 60%		

Eating processed canned food causes Hypertension

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	12	2.7
Disagree	68	15.5
Neutral	125	28.5
Agree	143	32.6
Strongly Agree	90	20.5
Total	438	100
Positive perception: 53.1%		

Exercise can reduce blood pressure

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	9	2.1
Disagree	27	6.2
Neutral	48	11.0
Agree	190	43.4
Strongly Agree	164	37.4
Total	438	100
Positive perception: 80.8%		

Fried foods increase risk of hypertension

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	6	1.4
Disagree	21	4.8
Neutral	94	21.5
Agree	223	50.9
Strongly Agree	94	21.5
Total	438	100
Positive perception: 72.4%		

Fruits and vegetables cannot help blood pressure

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	57	13.0
Agree	21	4.8
Neutral	58	13.2
Disagree	185	42.2
Strongly Disagree	117	26.7
Total	438	100
Positive perception: 68.9%		

Use of seasoning (i.e., Knorr cubes) increases blood pressure

Response	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	9	2.1
Disagree	56	12.8
Neutral	140	32.0
Agree	163	37.2
Strongly Agree	70	16.0
Total	438	100
Positive perception: 53.2%		

Tables 4 A, B, C, and D give details on the dietary behavior of the respondents in this study.

The analysis of seven common starchy foods (n = 438) in Table 4A below shows different consumption patterns. The results highlight strong preferences for both traditional and modern foods.

Rice is the most consumed food in the diet. Almost all people (88.1%) eat rice at least twice a week. A large number (18.0%) eat it every day. This shows that rice is a fundamental part of the diet, likely because it is versatile, and widely accepted. Spaghetti and Noodles (like Indomie) are often eaten. Spaghetti is consumed multiple times a week by 44.5% of people, and noodles by 27.2%. This shows that these modern, wheat-based foods are not just occasional meals. They are now a regular part of the weekly diet, reflecting changing tastes and convenience.

Traditional foods like beans, yams, and potatoes are usually eaten only once a week. 61.2% eat beans once a week, 62.8% eat yam once a week, while 78.3% eat potatoes once a week. This suggests these foods are no longer everyday staples.

Oatmeal shows a mixed pattern. Most people (59.8%) eat it only once a week. However, it has the highest number of people who rarely eat it (21.9%). It also has a small group of daily users (8.0%). This pattern suggests oatmeal is an emerging "health food." It is regularly eaten by a health-conscious group and very often by a small few. It is not yet a mainstream food for everyone.

Table 4A Starchy/Cereal/Grains

Rice

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	79	18.0	18.0
2-6 times a week	307	70.1	88.1
Once a week	49	11.2	99.3
Rarely	3	0.7	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Beans

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	12	2.7	2.7
2-6 times a week	152	34.7	37.4
Once a week	268	61.2	98.6
Rarely	6	1.4	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Yam

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	9	2.1	2.1
2-6 times a week	148	33.8	35.9
Once a week	275	62.8	98.7
Rarely	6	1.4	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Spaghetti

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	21	4.8	4.8
2-6 times a week	195	44.5	49.3
Once a week	207	47.3	96.6
Rarely	15	3.4	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Noodles (Indomie etc.)

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	31	7.1	7.1
2-6 times a week	119	27.2	34.3
Once a week	263	60.0	94.3
Rarely	25	5.7	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Potatoes

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	24	5.5	5.5
2-6 times a week	50	11.4	16.9
Once a week	343	78.3	95.2
Rarely	21	4.8	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Quaker Oats/Oat meals

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	35	8.0	8.0
2-6 times a week	45	10.3	18.3
Once a week	262	59.8	78.1
Rarely	96	21.9	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Table 4B shows the frequency of protein consumption. Eggs are the most frequently consumed protein. A very high 70.3% of people eat eggs at least twice a week, out of which 12.3% eat them daily. This shows that eggs are a major part of the diet because they are affordable and easy to prepare.

Meats (referring to red meat like beef or goat) are also often eaten. More than half of the people (54.8%) eat meat at least twice a week. However, the most common answer was "once a week" (43.8%). This suggests that while meat is popular, it is often eaten in a scheduled way, perhaps on weekends or special occasions, rather than every day. Chicken is eaten mostly once a week by most people (61.6%). Fewer people eat it multiple times a week (30.8%) compared to meat. This could be because of cost or personal preference.

Groundnut (peanuts) and soybeans are important plant-based proteins. Groundnut is consumed very regularly, with 57.5% eating it at least twice a week. Soybeans are eaten more moderately, with most people (57.3%) having them only once a week. This shows that groundnut is a more common everyday protein source than soybeans. Sausages/Hot dogs are the least common protein. Most people (59.8%) eat them only once a week, and a large number (25.8%) eat them rarely. This suggests that processed meats have not replaced these main protein sources for most people. They might be eaten as an occasional snack or convenience food, but they are not a main source of protein.

Table 4B Proteins**Red Meats**

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	75	17.1	17.1
2-6 times a week	165	37.7	54.8
Once a week	192	43.8	98.6
Rarely	6	1.4	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Chicken

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	21	4.8	4.8
2-6 times a week	135	30.8	35.6
Once a week	270	61.6	97.2
Rarely	12	2.7	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Groundnut

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	64	14.6	14.6
2-6 times a week	188	42.9	57.5
Once a week	177	40.4	97.9
Rarely	9	2.1	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Soyabeans

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	25	5.7	5.7
2-6 times a week	117	26.7	32.4
Once a week	251	57.3	89.7
Rarely	45	10.3	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Eggs

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	54	12.3	12.3
2-6 times a week	254	58.0	70.3
Once a week	124	28.3	98.6
Rarely	6	1.4	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Sausages / Hot dog

Frequency	Count	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	9	2.1	2.1
2-6 times a week	54	12.3	14.4
Once a week	262	59.8	74.2
Rarely	113	25.8	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Table 4C shows the frequency of consumption of fruits and vegetables. The majority of respondents, 56.8%, consume oranges once a week, followed by 33.6% consuming it 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption stands at 5.9%. 47.3% of respondents consume bananas once a week, with 36.1% consuming them 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption is relatively high at 15.3%. 55.3% of respondents consume watermelon once a week, followed by 36.1% consuming it 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption is at 5.7%. Majority of respondents, 65.1%, consume cucumber once a week, with 24.7% consuming it 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption stands at 5.5%. A significant portion, 67.4%, consume pineapples once a week, while 21.7% consume them 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption is at 8.2%. 52.3%, consume leafy greens 2-6 times a week, while 24.9% consume them daily.

Table 4C Fruits/Vegetables**Oranges**

Fruits/Vegetables	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	26	5.9	5.9
2-6 times a week	147	33.6	39.5
Once a week	249	56.8	96.3
Rarely	16	3.7	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Apple

Daily	19	4.3	4.3
2-6 times a week	95	21.7	26.0
Once a week	308	70.3	96.3
Rarely	16	3.7	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Pawpaw

Daily	25	5.7	5.7
2-6 times a week	119	27.2	32.9
Once a week	273	62.3	95.2
Rarely	21	4.8	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Grapes

Daily	6	1.4	1.4
2-6 times a week	48	11.0	12.4
Once a week	300	68.5	80.8
Rarely	84	19.2	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Banana

Daily	67	15.3	15.3
2-6 times a week	158	36.1	51.4
Once a week	207	47.3	98.6
Rarely	6	1.4	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Watermelon

Daily	25	5.7	5.7
2-6 times a week	158	36.1	41.8
Once a week	242	55.3	97.0
Rarely	13	3.0	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Cucumber

Daily	24	5.5	5.5
2-6 times a week	108	24.7	30.1
Once a week	285	65.1	95.2
Rarely	21	4.8	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Pineapple

Daily	36	8.2	8.2
2-6 times a week	95	21.7	29.9
Once a week	295	67.4	97.3
Rarely	12	2.7	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Pear

Daily	12	2.7	2.7
2-6 times a week	66	15.1	17.8
Once a week	336	76.7	94.5
Rarely	24	5.5	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Leafy Greens

Daily	109	24.9	24.9
2-6 times a week	229	52.3	77.2
Once a week	94	21.5	98.6
Rarely	6	1.4	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Many of the respondents, 52.1%, consume processed fruit juices once a week, followed by 35.8% who consume them 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption stands at 10.5%. Soft drink consumption is also common, with 39.0% of respondents consuming them once a week and 47.0% consuming them 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption is at 9.8%. A significant portion, 62.1%, consume energy drinks once a week, while 17.6% consume them 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption stands at 8.7%.

More than half of respondents, 58.2%, consume caffeinated drinks once a week, followed by 14.8% who consume them 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption is at 5.7%. A significant portion, 46.6%, never consumes alcohol. However, 45.2% consume it once a week, and 4.8% consume it 2-6 times a week. Daily consumption is at 3.4%.

Table 4D Beverages

Fruit Juices

Beverages	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Daily	46	10.5	10.5
2-6 times a week	157	35.8	46.3
Once a week	228	52.1	98.4
Rarely	7	1.6	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Soft Drinks

Daily	43	9.8	9.8
2-6 times a week	206	47.0	56.8
Once a week	171	39.0	95.8
Rarely	18	4.1	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Energy Drinks

Daily	38	8.7	8.7
2-6 times a week	77	17.6	26.3
Once a week	272	62.1	88.4
Rarely	51	11.6	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Caffeinated Drinks

Daily	25	5.7	5.7
2-6 times a week	65	14.8	20.5
Once a week	255	58.2	78.7
Rarely	93	21.2	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Alcohol

Daily	15	3.4	3.4
2-6 times a week	21	4.8	8.2
Once a week	198	45.2	53.4
Rarely	204	46.6	100.0
Total	438	100.0	100.0

Table 5 below shows the association between dietary behavior and level of knowledge across genders. A high score indicates that the individual consumes starchy foods and takes beverages almost on a daily basis, while a low score communicates otherwise.

Female respondents (n = 282): Among those with high starch & beverage scores (n = 170), 94 had high knowledge, 19 had low knowledge, and 57 had moderate knowledge. For those with low starch & beverage scores (n = 112), 73 had high knowledge, 6 had low knowledge, and 33 had moderate knowledge. The association was not statistically significant (p = 0.132).

Male respondents (n = 156): Among those with high starch & beverage scores (n = 90), 46 had high knowledge, 13 had low knowledge, and 31 had moderate knowledge. For those with low scores (n = 66), 29 had high knowledge, 13 had low knowledge, and 24 had moderate knowledge. This association was also not statistically significant (p = 0.583).

Overall (n = 438): Respondents with high starch & beverage scores (n = 260) recorded 140 with high knowledge, 32 with low knowledge, and 88 with moderate knowledge. Those with low scores (n = 178) had 102 with high knowledge, 19 with low knowledge, and 57 with moderate knowledge. Overall, the association was not statistically significant (p = 0.749).

Across all comparisons, there was no significant association (NS) between starch & beverage score levels and knowledge level among both male and female respondents.

Table 5 Association between dietary behavior and knowledge level

Gender			Knowledge Level			Total	p-value	Decision
			High	Low	Moderate			
Female	Starch & Beverage score level	High	94	19	57	170	0.132	NS
		Low	73	6	33	112		
	Total			167	25	90	282	
Male	Starch & Beverage score level	High	46	13	31	90	0.583	NS
		Low	29	13	24	66		
	Total			75	26	55	156	
Total	Starch & Beverage score level	High	140	32	88	260	0.749	NS
		Low	102	19	57	178		
	Total			242	51	145	438	

Female respondents (n = 282): Among females with high starch & beverage scores (n = 170), 12 had high perception, 34 had low perception, and 124 had moderate perception. For those with low scores (n = 112), 17 had high perception, 9 had low perception, and 86 had moderate perception. The association was statistically significant (p = 0.005), indicating that starch & beverage score level influences perception level among females.

Male respondents (n = 156): Among males with high scores (n = 90), 4 had high perception, 14 had low perception, and 72 had moderate perception. For those with low scores (n = 66), 3 had high perception, 17 had low perception, and 46 had moderate perception. This association was not statistically significant (p = 0.282).

Overall (n = 438): Respondents with high scores (n = 260) recorded 16 with high perception, 48 with low perception, and 196 with moderate perception. Those with low scores (n = 178) had 20 with high perception, 26 with low perception, and 132 with moderate perception. Overall, the association was not statistically significant (p = 0.118).

There was a significant association among females between starch & beverage score level and perception level, but no significant association among males.

Table 6 Association between dietary behavior and perception level across genders.

Gender			Perception level			Total	p-value	Decision
			High	Low	Moderate			
Female	Starch & Beverage score level	High	12	34	124	170	0.005	S
		Low	17	9	86	112		
	Total			29	43	210	282	
Male	Starch & Beverage score level	High	4	14	72	90	0.282	NS
		Low	3	17	46	66		

	Total		7	31	118	156		
Total	Starch & Beverage score level	High	16	48	196	260	0.118	NS
		Low	20	26	132	178		
	Total		36	74	328	438		

4. Discussion

This study found that 89% of participants had heard of hypertension, while 11% were unaware, highlighting a generally high level of baseline awareness. This aligns with a comprehensive Nigerian survey that reported awareness rates around 60%, with signs of improvement over time, notably closing the urban–rural gap (Awareness: 62.2% urban vs. 56.6% rural) (6).

However, awareness alone is insufficient; the results suggest that knowledge quality varies by source. The predominance of informal sources (“Others” – 62.6%) over formal education (20%) or digital media (social media 9.2%, internet 8.2%) raises concerns about information accuracy. This trend confirms findings from other LMIC contexts, where reliance on informal networks can perpetuate myths (e.g., beliefs in traditional cures) and impede evidence-based understanding (7).

A majority (69.6%) incorrectly believed hypertension manifests symptoms early. This is problematic given that hypertension is often a silent condition. Globally, around 46% of people with hypertension remain unaware of their condition. Misconceptions about symptoms may reduce screening uptake and delay diagnosis. In another study, only 40.1% recognized that hypertension might be asymptomatic (8).

The strong positive perception regarding salt reduction (92.4%) and exercise (80.8%) echoes the effectiveness of public health messaging around these modifiable risk factors. Salt-reduction interventions, including education, behavioral programs, and self-monitoring have demonstrated effectiveness in lowering both systolic and diastolic blood pressure in different places (9)

The moderate-to-high positive perceptions associated with fried foods (72.4%) and fruits and vegetables (68.9%) also reflect partial recognition of dietary impacts. The Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension (DASH) diet, rich in fruits, vegetables, and low-fat dairy, has been proven to significantly reduce blood pressure among individuals (10).

The belief that hypertension is more common among rich people (60% positive perception by disagreement) points to a shift from outdated paradigms. However, it underestimates current data showing that low socioeconomic status groups often bear a disproportionate hypertension burden.

The moderate awareness of processed or canned foods (53.1%) and seasoning (53.2%) as risk factors suggest these are underemphasized in public messaging. Given the high sodium content of such items, especially seasoning cubes, which are prevalent in some cultures, these knowledge gaps are concerning.

The high consumption of processed fruit juices, soft drinks, and energy drinks seen in the study reinforces the need for efforts to promote healthy beverage choices and limit the intake of sugary beverages, which are known contributors to hypertension risk. Meta-analytic data from cohort and cross-sectional studies highlight a consistent positive association between sugar-sweetened beverage consumption and hypertension (11).

The hypertensive effect of energy drinks is acute and well-documented, primarily due to the combination of high caffeine and sugar. A randomized controlled trial demonstrated that consuming 32 oz of a commercial energy drink resulted in a markedly higher elevation in blood pressure over 24 hours compared to a control caffeine beverage with the same amount of caffeine (12).

The dietary patterns observed among respondents in this study provide valuable insights into potential risk factors for hypertension. The majority of respondents consume rice and yam frequently, with substantial proportions consuming them 2-6 times a week or daily. Both rice and yam are starchy carbohydrates that can contribute to elevated blood glucose levels if consumed in large quantities. Excessive carbohydrate intake, especially refined carbohydrates, has been associated with insulin resistance and hypertension risk. The consumption of fruits such as oranges, bananas, watermelon, pineapples, and vegetables like cucumber and leafy greens is relatively high among respondents. These

foods are essential components of a balanced diet and are associated with lower hypertension risk due to their fiber, potassium, and antioxidant content.

The study revealed no statistically significant association between starch & beverage score levels and knowledge levels across gender groups ($p > 0.05$). While respondents with high starch & beverage scores appeared to have slightly higher proportions of high knowledge compared to those with low scores, these differences lacked statistical significance.

This suggests that dietary patterns related to starch and beverage consumption may not be strongly influenced by knowledge of hypertension or nutrition. Similar findings have been reported in studies where nutritional knowledge did not necessarily translate into healthier eating behaviors, indicating a gap between knowledge and practice (13;14).

Interestingly, previous research suggests that gender often influences nutrition knowledge and health-seeking behavior, with women typically exhibiting higher health literacy and healthier dietary choices (15,16). However, the current findings demonstrate that when starch & beverage scores were considered, gender did not modify the relationship between diet and knowledge level. This aligns with studies that emphasize the role of cultural, socioeconomic, and environmental factors over biological gender differences in shaping dietary behaviors and knowledge (17).

The lack of association may also reflect behavioral theories that knowledge alone is insufficient to change behavior. Factors such as taste preferences, food affordability, convenience, and cultural norms play a significant role in shaping dietary habits, regardless of knowledge level (14). This highlights the need for interventions that combine education with behavioral strategies, environmental changes, and affordability measures to encourage healthier food choices.

The findings revealed a significant association among females ($p = 0.005$) between starch & beverage score levels and perception levels, while the association among males ($p = 0.282$) and the overall population ($p = 0.118$) was not significant. This suggests that dietary patterns, specifically starch and beverage consumption, may influence perception toward hypertension and related health behaviors in women more than in men.

This result aligns with prior research indicating that women are often more responsive to health education and diet-related interventions compared to men (15). Women's greater involvement in meal preparation and household nutrition decisions could explain why their perceptions are more sensitive to dietary factors (17).

However, the lack of association among males and in the combined sample indicates that perception is influenced by multiple determinants beyond diet, including cultural norms, education, and socioeconomic status (14). The predominance of moderate perception levels (328 respondents overall) suggests that while awareness exists, it may not be strong enough to translate into consistently positive attitudes and behaviors toward hypertension prevention.

The significant relationship in females could reflect higher health consciousness and nutritional awareness among women, as observed in studies from similar contexts (15). On the other hand, the absence of such a relationship in men might point to a gender gap in how dietary practices shape perceptions. This gap underscores the need for gender-sensitive health promotion strategies that consider behavioral and social factors influencing perception.

Furthermore, the findings suggest that dietary interventions should integrate perception-shaping strategies, particularly among males, who may require more targeted communication to link their eating habits with health outcomes.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights both encouraging and concerning patterns regarding hypertension awareness, knowledge, and dietary behaviors. While awareness of hypertension was generally high, misconceptions, particularly the widespread belief that hypertension presents with early symptoms, pose a significant barrier to timely detection and management. The reliance on informal information sources over formal education or digital media further underscores the need for accurate, evidence-based health communication. Positive perceptions regarding salt reduction, exercise, and healthy food choices demonstrate the effectiveness of public health messaging in some areas. However, gaps remain in the understanding of risk factors such as processed foods, sugary beverages, and energy drinks, which continue to be widely consumed despite their well-documented links to hypertension.

Dietary patterns revealed frequent consumption of starchy carbohydrates alongside moderate intake of fruits and vegetables, suggesting both risks and protective factors within current eating habits. Importantly, the lack of a

significant association between starch and beverage consumption with knowledge levels indicates that awareness alone may not drive healthier choices. Gender differences in perception suggest that women may be more responsive to dietary influences on hypertension-related attitudes, pointing to the value of gender-sensitive interventions.

Overall, the findings affirm that improving hypertension outcomes requires more than raising awareness. Interventions must go beyond knowledge dissemination to address behavioral, cultural, and socioeconomic determinants of diet and health. Multi-faceted strategies, including accurate public messaging, affordability measures, behavioral support, and gender-tailored approaches, are essential for strengthening both knowledge and practice in hypertension prevention and control.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

The purpose of the research was explained to each respondent and verbal informed consent obtained from them before inclusion into the study. Also, anonymity of the respondents was assured and ensured. The confidentiality of the information they gave was also maintained.

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